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Evaluation of the effect of environmental pollution on water moss by time- and spectrally-resolved microscopy

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Posters**– 6. Advanced optical microscopy –****P-84****Evaluation of the effect of environmental pollution on water moss by time- and spectrally-resolved microscopy**

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Natural sensing of changes in endogenous fluorescence is a very effective tool for monitoring responsiveness of living organisms to environmental pollution, also including the presence of microplastics and/or heavy metals. Combination of spectral and time-resolved (FLIM) microscopy was applied on intrinsic fluorophores of the sweet water bryophyte species *Fontinalis antipyretica* moss leaves to provide information about their modification in the presence of chosen environmental stressors. Nanoparticles (NPs) from various metals (Zn, Ni, Co, Cu) were designed and fabricated by direct synthesis using femtosecond laser ablation in liquids. The effect of microplastics was evaluated using fluorescently labeled latex beads. We have observed differential effects of the chosen NPs on AF, as well as the capacity of the moss leaves to interact with microplastics. Gathered observations constitute the first step towards evaluation and proposal of new methodological approaches in optical microscopy for fast natural biosensing of the effects of environmental pollution directly in the water environment.

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P-86**Comprehensive fluorophore blinking analysis platform as a prerequisite for photoactivated localization microscopy**

René Platzer [2], Benedikt Rossboth [1], Eva Sevcik [1], Magdalena Schneider [1], Florian Baumgart [1], Hannes Stockinger [2], Gerhard J Schütz [1], Johannes B Huppa [2], Mario Brameshuber [1]

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Determining nanoscale protein distribution via Photoactivated Localization Microscopy (PALM) mandates precise knowledge of the applied fluorophore's blinking properties to counteract overcounting artifacts that distort the resulting biomolecular distributions.

Here, we present a readily applicable methodology to determine, optimize and quantitatively account for the blinking behavior of any PALM-compatible fluorophore. Using a custom-designed platform we revealed complex blinking of two photoswitchable fluorescence proteins (PS-CFP2 and mEOS3.2) and two photoactivatable organic fluorophores (PA Janelia Fluor 549 and Abberior CAGE 635) with blinking cycles on time scales of several seconds.

Incorporating such detailed information in our simulation-based analysis package allowed for robust evaluation of molecular clustering based on individually recorded single molecule localization maps.

P-85**A single-molecule approach to systematically study the narrow escape problem in micro-patterned model membranes**

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The narrow escape problem (NEP) is a common problem in biology and biophysics. It deals with Brownian particles confined to a domain with reflecting borders and one small escape window. The mean first passage time (τ), the mean time it takes a set of particles to escape, can be analytically calculated in 2D and 3D for several geometries. It depends on three parameters, which are the area of the domain, the size of the escape window, and the diffusion coefficient of the particle. We systematically tested the analytical solution of the NEP in 2D by variation of the escape opening (ϵ). Experiments were complemented by matching random walk simulations. For the experimental test, we prepared micro-patterned phospholipid bilayers from a combination of colloid lithography and vesicle fusion. We then imaged fluorescently labeled lipids diffusing in circular membrane patches using single-molecule fluorescence microscopy. We present our results on membrane patterning and show how lifetime limitation of fluorescent probes can be overcome. Namely with a correction factor which rescales the measured mean first passage time by the fraction of escaped particles. We found that the dependence of the mean first passage time on the escape opening agrees well with the theoretical prediction of $\ln(1/\epsilon)$. We present a comparison of our experimental and simulation results with the theoretical prediction for the mean first passage time.

P-87**Ultrafast particle tracking of single lipid molecules in membranes through ISCAT and MINFLUX microscopy**

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The diffusion dynamics of lipids on cellular membranes have always proven particularly challenging to study in optical microscopy, given the highly heterogeneous nature of their environment. Given the breadth of the relevant spatiotemporal scales to detect such heterogeneities, very few optical techniques are able to probe these intervals with single molecule level of detail. Interferometric Scattering (ISCAT) microscopy, for example, can reach kilohertz sampling rates with high signal to noise ratios. We employed this technique to probe the diffusion of single lipids on cellular membranes. Using a novel analysis approach to the single particle trajectories thus collected, we were able to uncover new details pertaining to the compartmentalization of the cellular membrane at the nanoscale. The recently developed MINFLUX offers a new outlook on this problem, thanks to the simultaneous reliance on non-invasive synthetic fluorescent tags, and high signal to noise ratios obtained through minimal photon fluxes. We will also show preliminary data to demonstrate the potential of this new approach to the detection of single particle diffusion in biological samples.